

SYNTHESIS OF LIGAND USING PYRIDINE -2-CARBOXYALDEHYDE AND SPECTROSCOPIC CHARACTERIZATION OF THEIR COBALT (II) COMPLEXES

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ABSTRACT

Co(II)Complexes have been synthesized with the ligand pyridine-2-carboxyaldehydethiosemicarbazone. The ligand and complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, determination of melting point, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility, Mass spectra, infrared and UV spectral studies. The molar conductance measurements in DMSO lies in the range of 7-11 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ Cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, which suggest the complexes to be non electrolyte in nature and being formulated as $[M(L)_2X_2]$. Where X= Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , SCN^- , ClO_4^- . The IR and other spectroscopic studies suggest bidentate nature of the ligand and the octahedral geometry of the complexes.

KEYWORDS: Copper (II) complexes, Pyridine-2-carboxyaldehydethiosemicarbazone, spectroscopic studies.

INTRODUCTION

Thiosemicarbazones are the Schiff bases, with general formula $R_1R_2C=N-NH-C(NH_2)=S$ capable of donating electron pair to the electron deficient sites. These are the condensation products of Thiosemicarbazide with various carbonyl compounds. These condensation products are very useful and versatile ligands as neutral or the anionic species.^{[1][2]} In the last three decades these have dragged attention of the researchers due to their – unique coordination tendency to behave either as monodentate, bidentate or tridentate ligand, capability to form chelate compounds having 5 to 6 membered ring, through their azomethine nitrogen and thione sulphur electron donating sites.^[1] Their distinctive biological and medicinal values, and pharmacological activities.^[3] Anti-cancer activities^{[4][5]}, anti-microbial activities.^{[6][7]} anti-fungal^{[8][9]}, antioxidant^[10] and cytotoxic activities^{[11][6]}, antiamebic activities^[12], application in Cyanide and Chloride Anion sensing activities^{[5][11]}, ability to form macrocyclic ligands having large spaces to accommodate metal ions.^[13] further increases their importance. Their capability can be utilized in biological systems^[14] to trap toxic metals. Their metal complexes have also been reported to show antitumor^[15] activities by inhibiting the action of ribonucleotide reductase^{[16][17]}, a vital enzyme in DNA synthesis. The activity of the complex is dependent on the Schiff base, carbonyl compound and substituent on it as well as the metal used in the compound.^[18]

Cobalt carry wider scope of use in clinical and medical researches. They have been reported to have very significant magnetic, redox, catalytic and imaging properties along with reported less toxicity, and can give versatile applications by varying their ligands environment.^[19]

The present paper discusses the synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of Cobalt metal complexes of Chloride, Bromide, Iodide, Perchlorate and Thiocyanate of Pyridine 2 carboxyaldehyde thiosemicarbazone as ligand.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material-All the chemicals used were of analytical grade and procured from Sigma Aldrich and E.Merck and used as received.

Synthesis of Schiff base ligands

2-formyl pyridine aldehyde thiosemicarbazone- 20 ml ethyl alcohol and 1.82 g(0.02 mole) of thiosemicarbazide taken in a Round bottom flask and heated at constant temperature(70⁰-80⁰c) for 1 hour. Also 2-formyl pyridine aldehyde(1.90ml) with minimum amount of ethanol is heated and refluxed simultaneously in separate flask. Solutions from both the flasks is mixed with constant stirring and refluxed for 8 hours and cooled in ice bath overnight. Off white or pale yellow coloured ligand is filtered out, washed and dried on vacuum.^[20]

Figure 1: Reaction Scheme.

Synthesis of complexes

0.002 mole(0.36g)of ligand (2:1) dissolved in minimum amount of hot ethanolic solution is mixed with 0.001 mole heated alcoholic solution of respective metal salts of Cobalt. The mixture is refluxed for 4-5 hours at a constant temperature. The mixture is cooled on ice bath and left over night.Precipitate filtered out and dried under vacuum. Purity of complex was checked with TLC and melting point was determined.

Physical Measurement

With Carlo Erba elemental analyser, the C,H and N content were determined. Magnetic susceptibility has been measured on Gouy Balance, using $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as calibrant. Molar conductance was measured on Systronic conductivity meter model 304. Mass spectrum has been recorded on JEOL, JMS, DX 303 mass spectrometer. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra of ligand was recorded on Bruker Advance Ultrashield 500 spectrometer using CDCl_3 as the solvent.IR spectra was recorded on FTIR BX-II spectrophotometer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ligand (Pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazone)- Ligand has been found to be stable at room temperature and are having high melting point. The IR spectra of ligand show band around 3347cm^{-1} and 3200 cm^{-1} , which are being attributed to NH₂ and NH groups respectively. The bands at 3116 and 2975 can be due to the C-H str vibrations. Band at 1261cm^{-1} , 1626 cm^{-1} and 698 cm^{-1} can be related to C=S, CH=N and Aromatic (pyridine ring) C=N bonds respectively.

Mass and NMR spectra -Mass spectra of ligand shows peak corresponding to removal of CSNH₂ group. The M^{++1} peak is observed at m/z 179.

NMR spectra gives peak at δ 8.446(s,1H, N(4)H),8.19(d,1HC(4)H),8.042(t,1H,C(3)H), 7.88(s,1HC(6)H), 7.79(d,1H,C(1)H), 7.59(m,1HC(2)H)11.82(s,1H,N(3)H)

Figure 3: NMR spectrum of the ligand.

Figure 4: IR spectrum of ligand.

Complexes

On the basis of elemental analysis and molecular weight determination the formula of the complexes is as suggested in table 1. The complexes have been found to be soluble in DMSO, and sparingly soluble in water and ethanol.

Molar conductance of complexes in DMSO is found in the range of $7-11 \Omega^{-1} \text{ Cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, which suggests its nonelectrolytic nature.(Table 3)^[21]

The IR spectrum of complexes-The band in ligand around 3347 cm^{-1} and 3116 cm^{-1} , attributed to NH_2 and NH groups do not show much shift in complexes. Band at 1626 cm^{-1} in the spectra of ligands show downward shift by about 20 cm^{-1} in the IR spectra of complex, indicating the involvement of azomethine Nitrogen in

complexation. The upward shift in band for pyridine nitrogen at 698 cm^{-1} , shows that it is also involved in coordination. Rest of the bands do not show much shift, showing the bidentate nature of ligand.(Table 2)In the spectrum of thiocyanate complex band at 2120 cm^{-1} shows coordinated thiocyanate anion.

The electronic spectral data in DMSO reveals its octahedral geometry showing three bands in the region $10398-11223 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $18100-18621 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $20320-21200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$, ${}^4\text{T}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}$, ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$.

The magnetic moment values lie in the range of 4.97-5.05 B.M. showing their paramagnetic nature with three unpaired electrons as expected.

Table 1: Analytical data and Melting Point of ligand and complexes.

Sl. No	Compound	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	Colour	M.P. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis %found (calculated)			
							Co(II)	C	H	N
1	PATS	$\text{C}_7\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{S}$	180	White	179	62	-	46.3 (46.66)	4.45 (4.48)	31.15 (31.12)
2	$[\text{Co}(\text{PATS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	$\text{CoC}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_8\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$	490	Reddish black	214	63	11.95 (12.02)	34.08 (34.30)	3.27 (3.29)	21.79 (22.85)
3	$[\text{Co}(\text{PATS})_2\text{Br}_2]$	$\text{CoC}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_8\text{S}_2\text{Br}_2$	579	Reddish brown	222	67	9.93 (10.17)	28.7 (29.03)	2.74 (2.78)	18.90 (19.35)
4	$[\text{Co}(\text{PATS})_2\text{I}_2]$	$\text{CoC}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_8\text{S}_2\text{I}_2$	673	brown	242	62	8.70 (8.75)	24.92 (24.98)	2.28 (2.40)	16.60 (16.64)
5	$[\text{Co}(\text{PATS})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	$\text{CoC}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_{10}\text{S}_4$	535.6	Greenish black	259	56	10.90 (11.0)	35.81 (35.88)	2.79 (3.01)	25.91 (26.15)
6	$[\text{Co}(\text{PATS})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$	$\text{CoC}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2\text{Cl}_2$	618.3	Black brown	212	64	9.42 (9.53)	27.02 (27.20)	2.50 (2.61)	17.76 (18.12)

Table 2: Infrared spectral data of complexes.

Compounds	N-H	C-H	C=S	CH=N	C=N AROMATIC
PATS	3347,3200	3116,2975	1261	1626	698
[CoL ₂ Cl ₂]	3340	3112	1259	1605	715
[CoL ₂ Br ₂]	3342	3114	1260	1608	721
[CoL ₂ I ₂]	3347	3114	1261	1611	718
[CoL ₂ (SCN) ₂]	3348	3118	1262	1606	714
[CoL ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	3342	3113	1256	1604	715

Table 3: Physical properties and electronic spectral data of complexes.

Complexes	Molar conductance $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$	Magnetic moment(B.M.)	Electronic spectral data (λ_{max} in cm^{-1})		
[CoL ₂ Cl ₂]	7	5.03	10398	18621	21200
[CoL ₂ Br ₂]	11	4.99	10981	18214	20640
[CoL ₂ I ₂]	9	4.97	11223	18118	20320
[CoL ₂ (SCN) ₂]	9	4.99	10820	18341	21188
[CoL ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	7	5.05	11120	18100	21020

CONCLUSION

The spectroscopic studies show bidentate nature of ligands, binding through its azomethine and pyridine nitrogen. Thione sulphur is suggested to be uncoordinated. The molar conductance values prove nonelectrolytic complex and magnetic moments give

information about paramagnetic nature of complex with 3 unpaired electrons. Electronic spectra provide information about the octahedral geometry of complex. Thus on the basis of above observations and spectroscopic studies the proposed structure of the complex is as follows

Where X= Cl⁻ Br⁻ I⁻ SCN⁻ ClO₄⁻

Figure 2: Proposed structure of complex with octahedral geometry and non electrolytic nature

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